

Salt, Gandhi & British Raj: Special Reference to 1930

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ABSTRACT

Salt is a commodity that had been taxed in India since the time of the Mauryas period. Taxes on salt have been common even during the time of Chandragupta Maurya. The Arthashastra, which give an account of the different duties of the people, says that a special officer called lavananadhyaksa was appointed to collect the salt tax.¹ Taxes were also forced on imported salt. However, they accounted for 25 percent of the total cost of the salt.

Key Words: Salt, Mauryas Period, Tax.

Historical background

In Bengal, there was a salt tax in rage during the era of the Mughal Empire, which was 5% for Hindus and 2.5% for Muslims.² In 1759, two years after its conquest at the Battle of Plassey, the British East India Company came into control of land near Calcutta where there were salt works. Utilizing this opportunity to make money, they two-layered the land rent and compulsory transit charges on the transportation of salt.³

In 1764, following the triumph at the Battle of Buxar, the British began to control all the revenues of Bengal, Bihar and Orissa. Robert Clivel in 1765, made the sale of tobacco, betel nut, and salt, the monopoly of the senior officers of the British East India Company. Contracts were given to deliver salt to depots, and merchants were mandatory to buy from these depots.

In 1772, the then Governor-General Warren Hastings brought the salt trade once again under the Company's control. The salt works were let out to farmers who agreed to deliver salt at a fixed rate to the Company and sold the leases to the highest bidders. Corruption dealt a severe blow to the Company and the revenue from salt trade fell to 80,000 rupees by 1780.⁴ This, along with the exploitation of the salt India. In 1780 Hastings brought the salt trade once again under government control, dividing the infrastructure into Agencies each under the control of an agent and governed by a Controller. This system persisted, with minor modifications, until India's independence in 1947.

Practicing Satyagraha

Before leading the Indian freedom movement, Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi used to live in South Africa to fight against injustice and class division. Within 10 years, Gandhi propagated the philosophy of Satyagraha there and moved the country towards a no class or ethnic discrimination society. Gandhi arrived in Durban aboard SS Safari in 1893. In no time, Gandhi became the leader of the South African Indian community.

¹ Thomas R. Trautmann, *Arthashastra: The Science of Wealth*, Penguin Books Limited, London, 2016, p.46.

² Parthasarathi Shome, *Taxation History, Theory, Law and Administration*, Springer International Publishing, London, 2021, p.30.

³ *Ibid.*, p.37.

⁴ Mary Rochester, "The Salt Tax", Salt Museum Publication, A Salt Museum Publication, Cheshire Libraries.

His involvement in the non-violent movement in South Africa, he is looked up to as a leader there. From 1893 to 1914, Gandhi worked as an attorney and a public worker. In a meeting in New Delhi, Gandhi said he was born in India but was made in South Africa.⁵

Gandhi and he set up Phoenix Farm near Durban (South Africa). Here, Gandhi would train his cadres on non-violent Satyagraha or peaceful restraint. Phoenix Farm is considered as the birthplace of Satyagraha. However, it was at the Tolstoy Farm, Gandhi's second camp in South Africa, where Satyagraha was moulded into a weapon of protest. In September 1906, Gandhi organised the first Satyagraha campaign to protest against the Transvaal Asiatic ordinance that was constituted against the local Indians. Again in June 1907, he held Satyagraha against the Black Act. After years of protests, the government imprisoned hundreds of Indians in 1913, including Gandhi. Under pressure, the South African government accepted a compromise negotiated by Gandhi and General Jan Christian Smuts that included recognition of Hindu marriages and the abolition of a poll tax for Indians.

When Gandhi sailed from South Africa in 1914 to return home, Smuts wrote, "The saint has left our shores, I sincerely hope forever."⁶ At the outbreak of World War I, Gandhi spent several months in London. In 1915 Gandhi founded an ashram in Ahmadabad, India, that was open to all castes. Wearing a simple loincloth and shawl, Gandhi lived an austere life devoted to prayer, fasting and meditation. He became known as "Mahatma," which means "great soul." In 1919, with India still under the firm control of the British, Gandhi had a political reawakening when the newly enacted Rowlatt Act authorized British authorities to imprison people suspected of sedition without trial. In response, Gandhi called for a Satyagraha campaign of peaceful protests and strikes.

Violence broke out instead, which culminated on April 13, 1919, in the Massacre of Amritsar. Troops led by British Brigadier General Reginald Dyer fired machine guns into a crowd of unarmed demonstrators and killed nearly 400 people. No longer able to pledge allegiance to the British government, Gandhi returned the medals he earned for his military service in South Africa and opposed Britain's mandatory military draft of Indians to serve in World War I.

⁵ J. N. Uppal, Gandhi Ordained in South Africa, Publications Division Ministry of Information & Broadcasting, New Delhi, 1995, p.16.

⁶ Uma Majmudar, Gandhi's Pilgrimage of Faith: From Darkness to Light, State University of New York Press, New York, 2005, p.144

Gandhi became a leading figure in the Indian home-rule movement. Calling for mass boycotts, he urged government officials to stop working for the Crown, students to stop attending government schools, soldiers to leave their posts and citizens to stop paying taxes and purchasing British goods. Rather than buy British-manufactured clothes, he began to use a portable spinning wheel to produce his own cloth. The spinning wheel soon became a symbol of Indian independence and self-reliance.⁷

The Indian National Congress

Gandhi assumed the leadership of the Indian National Congress and advocated a policy of non-violence and non-cooperation to achieve home rule. After British authorities arrested Gandhi in 1922, he pleaded guilty to three counts of sedition. Although sentenced to a six-year imprisonment, Gandhi was released in February 1924 after appendicitis surgery. He discovered upon his release that relations between India's Hindus and Muslims devolved during his time in jail. When violence between the two religious groups flared again, Gandhi began a three-week fast in the autumn of 1924 to urge unity. He remained away from active politics during much of the latter 1920s. In 1928, for the first time a constitution for India was drafted by Nehru Committee that was headed by Motilal Nehru. A year later, in the Lahore session Jawaharlal Nehru was elected as president of the Congress. The congress passed the Poona Swaraj Resolution in December 1929, it was a month later on January 26, 1930, when a Pledge of Indian The declaration included the readiness to withhold taxes, and the statement: The Congress Working Committee gave Gandhi the responsibility for coordinating the first act of civil disobedience, with Congress itself ready to take charge after Gandhi's anticipated arrest. Gandhi's plan was to begin civil disobedience with a Satyagraha aimed at the British salt tax. The

1882 Salt Act gave the British a monopoly on the collection and manufacture of salt, limiting its handling to government salt depots and levying a salt tax.⁸ Violation of the Salt Act was a criminal offence. Even though salt was freely available to those living on the coast (by evaporation of sea water), Indians were forced to buy it from the colonial government. Initially, Gandhi's choice of the salt tax was met with incredulity by the Working Committee of the Congress.

However, Gandhi had sound reasons for his decision. An item of daily use could resonate more

with all classes of citizens than an abstract demand for greater political rights. The salt tax represented 8.2% of the British Raj tax revenue, and hurt the poorest Indians the most significantly.⁹ Explaining his choice, Gandhi said, “Next to air and water, salt is perhaps the greatest necessity of life.”

Gandhi felt that this protest would dramatise Purnaswaraj in a way that was meaningful to every Indian. He also reasoned that it would build unity between Hindus and Muslims by fighting a wrong that touched them equally. After the protest gathered steam, the leaders realised the power of salt as a symbol. Nehru remarked about the unprecedented popular response, “it seemed as though a spring had been suddenly released.

Violation of the Salt Act

Gandhi planned a new Satyagraha campaign. The Salt March that entailed a 390- kilometer/240-mile march to the Arabian Sea, where he would collect salt in symbolic defiance of the government monopoly.¹⁰ “My ambition is no less than to convert the British people through non-violence and thus make them see the wrong they have done to India,” he wrote days before the march to the British viceroy, Lord Irwin. Wearing a homespun white shawl and sandals and carrying a walking stick, Gandhi set out from his religious retreat in Sabarmati on March 12, 1930, with a few dozen followers. By the time he arrived 24 days later in the coastal town of Dandi, the ranks of the marchers swelled, and Gandhi broke the law by making salt from evaporated seawater. The Salt March sparked similar protests, and mass civil disobedience swept across India. Approximately 60,000 Indians were jailed for breaking the Salt Acts, including Gandhi, who was imprisoned in May 1930.¹¹ Still, the protests against the Salt Acts elevated Gandhi into a transcendent figure around the world. He was named Time magazine’s “Man of the Year” for 1930. The civil disobedience in 1930 marked the first time women became mass participants in the struggle for freedom. British documents show that the British government was shaken by satyagraha. Nonviolent protest left the British confused about whether or not to jail Gandhi. John Court Curry, a British police officer stationed in India.

⁸Thomas Weber, *On the Salt March: The Historiography of Gandhi's March to Dandi*, Rupa & Company, Delhi, 2009, p.52.

Sarojini Sinha, *A Pinch of Salt Rocks an Empire*, Children's Book Trust, Delhi, 1985, p.1

wrote in his memoirs that he felt nausea every time he dealt with Congress demonstrations in 1930. Curry and others in British government, including Wedgwood Benn, Secretary of State for India, preferred fighting violent rather than nonviolent opponents.¹⁴

Salt Satyagraha succeeded in drawing the attention of the world. Millions saw the newsreels showing the march. Time declared Gandhi its 1930 Man of the Year, comparing Gandhi's march to the sea "to defy Britain's salt tax as some New Englanders once defied a British tea tax".¹⁵ Civil disobedience continued until early 1931, when Gandhi was finally released from prison to hold talks with Irwin. It was the first time the two held talks on equal terms and resulted in the Gandhi–Irwin Pact. The talks would lead to the Second Round Table Conference at the end of 1931.

Salt Satyagraha produced scant progress toward dominion status or self-rule for India, and did not win any major concessions from the British.¹⁶ It also failed to attract Muslim support. Congress leaders decided to end satyagraha as official policy in 1934. Nehru and other Congress members drifted further apart from Gandhi, who withdrew from Congress to concentrate on his Constructive Programme, which included his efforts to end untouchability in the Harijan movement. Even though British authorities were again in control by the mid-1930s, Indian, British, and world opinion increasingly began to recognise the legitimacy of claims by Gandhi and the Congress Party for sovereignty and self-rule. The Satyagraha campaign of the 1930s also forced the British to recognise that their control of India depended entirely on the consent of the Indians – Salt Satyagraha was a significant step in the British losing that consent.¹⁷

Nehru considered the Salt Satyagraha the high-water mark of his association with Gandhi, and felt that its lasting importance was in changing the attitudes of Indians of course these movements exercised tremendous pressure on the British Government

¹⁴ Gene Sharp, *Gandhi Wields the Weapon of Moral Power; Three Case Histories*, Creative Media Partners, LLC, 2021.

¹⁵ Neal Bascomb, *The Salt Thief: Gandhi's Heroic March to Freedom*, Scholastic Incorporated, 2024.

¹⁶ Richard Bartlett Gregg, *The Power of Nonviolence*, Cambridge University Press, London, 2018.

¹⁷ Ananda Raj, *Op.cit.*, p.78.

and shook the government machinery.¹⁸ But the real importance, to my mind, lay in the effect they had on our own people, and especially the village masses ... Non-cooperation dragged them out of the mire and gave them self-respect and self-reliance ... They acted courageously and did not submit so easily to unjust oppression; their outlook widened and they began to think a little in terms of India as a whole ... It was a remarkable transformation and the Congress, under Gandhi's leadership, must have the credit for it.

Conclusion resulted the most important laws, acts and unity among Indian subcontinent. In response to the inadequacy of the Simon Report, the Labour Government, which had come to power under Ramsay MacDonald in 1929, decided to hold a series of Round Table Conferences in London.

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Vithalbhai Patel, former Speaker of the Assembly, watched the beatings and remarked, "All hope of reconciling India with the British Empire is lost forever." Miller's first attempts at telegraphing the story to his publisher in England were censored by the British telegraph operators in India. Only after threatening to expose British censorship was his story allowed to pass. The story appeared in 1,350 newspapers all over the world and was read into the official record of the United States Senate by Senator John J. Blaine.

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¹⁸ Anuj Ambalal, Rijuta Mehta, 23 Grams of Salt: Retracing Gandhi's March to Dandi, Navajivan Trust, Ahmedabad, 2020

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Nehru considered the Salt Satyagraha the high-water mark of his association with Gandhi and felt that its lasting importance was in changing the attitudes of Indians. Of course these movements exercise tremendous pressure on the British Government and shook the government machinery. But the real importance, to my mind, lay in the effect they had on our own people, and especially the village masses ... Non-cooperation dragged them out of the sludge and gave them self-respect and self-reliance. They acted audaciously and did not submit so easily to unjust tyranny, their outlook widened and they began to think a little in terms of India as a whole, It was a remarkable transformation and the Congress, under Gandhi's leadership, must have the credit for it. More than thirty years later, Satyagraha and the March to Dandi exercised a strong influence on American civil rights activist Martin Luther King Jr., and his fight for civil rights for blacks in the 1960s.

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